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Abstract. Changes occurring in the economic, social, political, scientific, and cultural spheres of society influence the development of language. For instance, in the process of globalization, numerous new words, terms, and concepts are entering our language, leading to its enrichment based on these new concepts. In turn, this phenomenon demonstrates the significant role of sociolinguistic factors in language development. The causes of changes in the national language are linked to various factors, such as political, social, cultural, and technological conditions, and these factors are complex in nature. The article explores the historical development, current state, and the place and role of the community in the evolution of the national language.

Keywords: media language, language of interethnic communication, national language, sociolinguistic factors, linguistic sign, language policy, language development, linguistic phenomenon, Uzbek language

Currently, consistent reforms are being implemented in Uzbekistan aimed at strengthening the role of the Uzbek language in society and on the international stage. The state language plays a crucial role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and loyalty to national traditions and values. In the context of building a new Uzbekistan, it is essential to preserve and enrich the purity of the state language, maintain and develop the languages of nations and ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan, create necessary conditions for learning Uzbek as the state language, and define strategic goals, priorities, and stages of development. It should be particularly emphasized that the policy of developing state support for other languages alongside Uzbek fully aligns with public interests. In our view, special attention should be paid to the historical and legal aspects of national statehood development. It is known that in the territory of modern Uzbekistan, the local population has long spoken several languages and used them in official domains. Creating the necessary conditions for developing the ability to freely speak and think in two or more native languages is one of the most important tasks of the state's modern language policy. Indeed, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "We view the development of the Uzbek language as interconnected with the development of other languages and cultures."

Despite the Uzbek language holding a leading position, especially in official documents and education, out of the functioning schools, 8,867 conduct education in Uzbek, 739 in Russian, 383 in Karakalpak, 505 in Kazakh, 267 in Tajik, 62 in Kyrgyz, and 50 in Turkmen. In higher education institutions, the educational process is organized in Uzbek and Russian, while in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, instruction is provided in Karakalpak, Uzbek, and Russian. Additionally, many universities have departments and groups that offer education in local ethnic group languages - Kazakh, Tajik, and Turkmen. This situation demonstrates that the state is directing taxpayers' funds towards effectively fulfilling important tasks in the realm of language policy. It should be emphasized that ... "in a multinational environment, the Russian language holds a special place in modern socio-political and cultural life as a mediating language and a conduit for scientific and technical information.". In Uzbekistan, Russian is considered the language of international communication. It

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VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

performs certain official functions permitted by official documents and is regarded as the country's second language. For over a century and a half, Russian has primarily influenced the Uzbek language in terms of alphabet selection, vocabulary, and anthroponymy.

Considering that Russian speakers constitute a significant portion of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to separately address the relationship between the Uzbek language and Russian, as well as the lexical fund of bilingual speakers. Typical concepts, realities, and phenomena borrowed between Russian and Uzbek languages were not formed independently, but as a result of centuries-old mutual cultural ties between the two peoples. Realia can be considered as examples of such units. Their active use in the media space is explained by their application in education, medicine, justice, tourism, international relations, and other spheres within our country. "Uzbek mentality, rules of conduct, respect for elders, consideration of gender aspects, and various customs are observed in oral and written communication." In the Uzbek media sphere, the influence of Uzbek realia on the development of the Russian language and their manifestation in newspaper language is also viewed as a cultural code. It is evident that sociolinguistic factors play a crucial role in language development, as language, being a social phenomenon, is closely intertwined with society and its changes. Sociolinguistic factors in language development are reflected in the works of G. Leffler. The German linguist defines sociolinguistics as the "theory of social activity," wherein language is viewed as one of the elements of social structure. Additionally, it is emphasized that it is important to understand that language is regarded not only as a means of communication but also as an integral part of society's life.

The social factor plays an important role in the development of language. "The main characteristic of the social factor is the speech process, possibility, conditions, situation, and time." Indeed, these signs play a crucial role in obtaining, storing, modifying, and transmitting information. Naturally, we deemed it appropriate to elaborate on the concept of the linguistic sign in this context. The linguistic sign is a fundamental concept in linguistics, and its role in the development of national languages is immeasurable. A linguistic sign is the basic unit of language that connects a specific concept (meaning) with a certain acoustic form (articulation), thereby enabling the transmission of ideas and information between people. This concept was developed in the work of Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure, who is considered the founder of modern structural linguistics. In our opinion, language policy is one of the social factors influencing the functioning and development of languages. It affects the evolution of the language system. "Languages did not develop under the eternal and unchanging laws of nature, but rather evolved alongside the flourishing of peoples, sometimes rapidly progressing, other times slowing down as a result of these peoples' savagery, and thus they experienced both joyful moments of advancement and tedious periods of stagnation."

The development of the literary language in Uzbekistan, as in any multinational country, is a priority for the state and one of the pressing issues for society in terms of language policy. Supporting the Uzbek language as the state language should be at the forefront of the country's modern language policy. Understanding the changes occurring in the national language during the process of language development and their causes is of great importance for linguists. Conducting research while adhering to a descriptive approach is determined by the significance of such changes for the linguistic community. Traditionally, linguists focus on the diachronic and synchronic aspects of language and the study of its evolution over time. The reasons for changes in the national language are associated with numerous factors, such as political, social, cultural, and technological conditions, and these factors are complex in nature. Additionally, extralinguistic and linguistic factors can be included

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

among the sociolinguistic factors of language development. It is known that extralinguistic factors can be viewed as parameters of social reality, which determine both the general and specific levels of changes in language. Their influence leads to the transformation of the entire language system or its significant components.

A. Nurmonov emphasizes that realizing the potential of the Uzbek language and establishing the norms of the Uzbek literary language was one of the priority tasks in the 1920s and 1930s, and the main role in addressing this issue fell primarily to the press. It should be emphasized that during that period, the development of the Uzbek literary language was not confined solely to standardization tasks, but was also closely tied to bringing the literary language closer to the conversational language. This process reflected the changes in the social and cultural environment of Uzbekistan. Indeed, "the formation of literary norms occurred through a gradual abandonment of archaic forms and the adoption of elements from the vernacular. This helped make literature comprehensible and accessible to a broad readership and laid the foundation for the emergence of a new literary tradition." Indeed, the Uzbek language has been shaped by various factors, including invasions and cultural contacts from different periods. Initially, the Uzbek language was under the strong influence of Persian, and later it was influenced by Arabic, which was reflected in its lexical composition and spelling. After joining the USSR in the 20th century, it came under the influence of Russian, and Russification became part of state policy.

It is known that during the Soviet period, there was a significant change in the writing system of the Uzbek language. In the late 1920s, a transition was made from the Arabic alphabet to the Latin script, and in 1940 to the Cyrillic script. This process was connected with the Soviet government's language policy in the republics. After gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan revised its language policy, declared Uzbek the state language, and adopted a program to support and develop it. In 1993, the transition to the Latin script began, which signified Uzbekistan's emergence from the influence of the USSR and its integration into the international community. The Latin script was aimed at simplifying the study of the Uzbek language for foreigners and reducing dependence on Russian in the country's national education system.

It should be noted that the modern language policy of Uzbekistan pursues the following main goals:

- *Strengthening the role of the Uzbek language as the state language.* This means actively using the language in all spheres of public life - from education to *administrative management*.
- *Developing and supporting Uzbek vocabulary and terminology.* This involves creating new terminological dictionaries, especially to promote Uzbek alternatives to words borrowed from English and Russian.
- *Multilingualism.* Uzbekistan is a multinational country, and its language policy also aims to support languages such as Russian, Karakalpak, Tajik, and Kazakh. This contributes to the preservation of cultural diversity and interethnic harmony.
- *Adapting the language to modern scientific and technical realities.* This requires not only introducing new terms and borrowed words but also creating a comprehensive system for their use. This will help strengthen the scientific and technological base in the Uzbek language.

Linguistic factors also play an important role in the process of language development, influencing the formation, change, and enrichment of language with new lexical and grammatical rules. Linguistic factors are related to the internal structure of language, including aspects such as phonetics, morphology, syntax, and lexicology. These factors influence the stability of language and its development in various ways. Different circumstances in the functioning of language affect the

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

language system. These conditions influencing language development are called language factors or factors of language development. The development of language is accompanied by two important processes: differentiation and integration:

a) The process of differentiation is characterized by an intensification of differences between languages and dialects and an increase in the number of languages. Differentiation facilitates the separation of individual language systems, which leads to the formation of new languages based on existing languages and dialects;

b) the process of integration of languages and their characteristic features manifests through a reduction in the number of languages. Integration often results in the merging of languages, where a new language is formed on the basis of several languages. A striking example of this is the emergence of the French language as a result of the interaction between the Gallic and Latin languages. Such processes are observed even in the modern era. For instance, in the process of globalization, American English elements are influencing various languages, forming elements of a common language of communication.

In language development, linguistic factors modify, renew, and enrich its internal and external structure. Phonetic, morphological, syntactic, and lexical changes ensure the language's adaptation to modern requirements, while social and cultural influences enable it to respond to society's needs. The evolution of language and its changes under various factors contribute to the enrichment of national culture and societal development.

Indeed, within the sociolinguistic framework, the state of media language, its priorities or, conversely, its limitations - that is, the analysis of scholars' views on extralinguistic phenomena – arouses great interest. It should be noted that the sociolinguistic study of media language is a powerful tool for analyzing various linguistic phenomena, such as the manifestation of language tools in the information space, as well as its influence on public opinion, social lexicon, style, and language norms that can reflect social standards and cultural values.

According to D.M. Teshabaeva, ... “sociolinguistics studies how language undergoes modifications in the process of mass communication depending on the social characteristics of communicants, the features of the communication situation, the communication channel, the content of information, and other social factors.”. Indeed, the connection between language phenomena and social factors has been well-established by linguists worldwide. By social factors, we primarily refer to various social relationships among people. Therefore, the sociolinguistic approach to studying media language serves as a crucial means of understanding linguistic phenomena in modern society. It can help to better comprehend how language is used in the media, as well as how it influences public opinion and culture. Furthermore, the use of words and phrases, based on the analysis of linguistic means in the media space, enhances the informational value and impacts audience behavior.

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